

HORIZON 2020

Research and Innovation action

Grant Agreement No. 730965

ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium:

**A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research
in the Arctic**

**Deliverable 8.8. Progress report on dissemination
activities**

Submission of Deliverable

Work Package	WP8
Deliverable no. & title	D8.8. Progress report on dissemination activities
Version	V1
Creation Date	01.12.2019
Last change	10.01.2020
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP lead accepted <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Executive Board accepted
Dissemination level	<input type="checkbox"/> PU-Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP- Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE- Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO- Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	AWI
Contributors	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input type="checkbox"/> 2 – SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 - NPI, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 - ULAAVAL, <input type="checkbox"/> 5 – UAF/CFOS, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 6 – AP, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 – CSIC-UTM, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – CNR, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - WOC, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – IOPAN, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – FMI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 – NERC-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – DTU-AQUA, <input type="checkbox"/> 15 – ARCTIA
Due date	31.12.2019
Delivery date	21.01.2020

1. Introduction

As an international, transdisciplinary project based on networking activities, transnational access and joint research activities, ARICE fosters and depends on an active cooperation with key stakeholders as well as a regular dissemination of relevant information and results from the onset on.

The primary communication and engagement goals fall into three broad areas:

- **Corporate communication**, which is set to generate a global visibility for ARICE;
- **Internal communication**, which aims at facilitating an effective interaction among participant institutions;
- **External communication**, which enables engagement activities with stakeholders, the media and the public.

This progress report on dissemination activities reviews activities of the past 24 months of the project, which **targeted both the area of corporate and of external communication**. It looks at dissemination activities at conferences and events, online outreach (including the ARICE website, social media channels and email newsletter), media relations and outreach materials.

2. Dissemination activities at conferences and events

Over the past two years, the ARICE consortium members have been actively engaged in promoting the project's work at ca. 50 national, European and international conferences and workshops.

The consortium members have, in addition to presenting the objectives and advances of ARICE at external events, distributing promotional materials and representing the project at panel discussions, also organised sessions and workshops at or associated to a range of conferences, which were targeted mainly at stakeholders.

Dissemination activities involving the organization of a ARICE workshop or session at conferences and events are listed below:

Name of event	Date	Location	Audience
International Research Ship Operators' Meeting https://www.irso.info/irso-2018/	04.10.2018	Barcelona, Spain	Operators of research vessels in the Arctic
Activity: ARICE organized one workshop entitled "Workshop: Towards an European Network of Polar Research Vessels in the Arctic"			
Aim of the workshop: - to discuss ways of cooperation between institutes operating PRVs and potential non-national users, making use of experiences from other initiatives for pooling and harmonisation of resources of costly research infrastructures. - exploring the specific interests and potentials of the EU Arctic PRVs operators to implement a common European network of Polar Research Vessels (PRVs) to better coordinate the existing polar research fleet, avoiding duplication of efforts.			

ARICE Participants at the event and their role

Nicole Biebow (AWI) – presenter/organizer
 Verónica Willmott (AWI) - presenter/organizer
 Katarina Garfeld (SPRS) - presenter
 Karen Edelvang (DTU-Aqua) - presenter

Name of event	Date	Location	Audience
Sustainable Ocean Summit 2018 https://www.oceancouncil.org/event/sustainable-ocean-summit-2018/	15-11-2018	Hong Kong, China	Industry representatives
Activity: Session entitled: SMART Ocean – SMART Industries and the Arctic: Advancing Industry-Science Collaboration for Data Collection in Support of Safe and Responsible Arctic Development			
Aim of the workshop: The aim of this workshop was to discuss how industry could better engage in data collection in the Arctic in support of safe and responsible shipping, the benefits and barriers to closer business cooperation with researchers, and the priority locations, topics and technology to engage more ships and platforms of opportunity in collecting data in the Arctic.			
ARICE Participants at the event and their role Christine Valentin (WOC) – Organizer/presenter Paul Holtus (WOC) – Organizer/presenter Verónica Willmott – presenter Nicole Biebow (AWI) - presenter Annu Oikonen (FMI) - presenter			

Name of event	Date	Location	Audience
American Geophysical Union Fall meeting https://agu.confex.com/agu/fm18/meetingapp.cgi	10-14.12.2018	Washington, DC, USA	Scientific community, policy makers, science managers
Activity: Joint booth among INTERACT, EPB and ARICE			
Aim: To effectively communicate, the transnational access opportunities in ARICE to the scientific community.			
ARICE Participants at the event and their role Verónica Willmott – organizer / booth representative Nicole Biebow (AWI) – booth representative			

Name of event	Date	Location	Audience
European Research Vessel Operators (ERVO) 2019 meeting http://www.ervo-group.eu/np4/np4/np4/44.html	11-06-2019	Hamburg, Germany	Operators of European Research Vessels
Activity: ARICE Workshop: Towards facilitating long term sharing on planning information of European Polar Research Vessels			
Aim of the workshop: This workshop explores the needs, possible obstacles and ways for a better coordination of the European Arctic research fleet. It includes brief presentations of what the harmonization of the European research fleet entails, who can benefit from increased cooperation, and the possible ways of reaching this goal. This will be followed by an open discussion.			
ARICE materials distributed: flyers			
ARICE Participants at the event and their role Justiina Dahl (SPRS) – organizer / presenter Verónica Willmott – organizer/presenter Nicole Biebow (AWI) – organizer Karen Edelvang (DTU-Aqua) – presenter Miki Ojeda (UTM-CSIC) - presenter			

Name of event	Date	Location	Audience
Arctic Circle Assembly 2019 http://www.arcticcircle.org/	11.10.2019	Reykjavik, Iceland	Industry representatives, scientific community, policy makers
Activity: Joint session organized as a collaborative effort among EU Polar Cluster members: ARICE, KEPLER, ARCSAR, with ExtremeEarth Breaking the Ice: cooperation for safe and responsible exploitation of Arctic Sea routes			
Aim of the workshop: This breakout session will showcase the needs of a collaborative science-industry approach in addressing accurate sea-ice and weather predictions, information on the status of the Arctic and its marine life, and complex predictions of future scenarios. It aims at fostering active discussions on how the science community can better address the needs of industry, and at identifying opportunities for collaboration between the science community, ice mapping agencies, and industry.			
ARICE Participants at the event and their role Verónica Willmott – organizer Nicole Biebow (AWI) – presenter Christine Valentin (WOC) - participant Massimo Caccia (CNR) – participant Halldór Jóhannson (AP) – participant			

Name of event	Date	Location	Presenters
Sustainable Ocean Summit 2019 https://www.sustainableoceansummit.org/	20-11-2019	Paris, France	Verónica Willmott (AWI) Annu Oikonen (FMI) Christine Valentin (WOC) Paul Holtus (WOC)
Activity: ARICE session entitled: Towards a sustainable development of the Arctic: providing Europe with better capacities for marine-based research in the ice covered Arctic Ocean			
Aim of the workshop: The identification of joint industry and science community priorities for Arctic research and observations:			
ARICE Participants at the event and their role Christine Valentin (WOC) – Organizer/presenter Paul Holtus (WOC) – Organizer/presenter Verónica Willmott – presenter Nicole Biebow (AWI) - presenter Annu Oikonen (FMI) – presenter Massimo Caccia (CNR) – Presenter Halldór Jóhannson (AP) - presenter			

Name of event	Date	Location	Presenters
Aci 15 th Arctic Shipping Summit https://www.wplgroup.com/aci/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2019/11/MASe7-Agenda.pdf	04/05-12-2019	Hamburg, Germany	Halldor Johannsson (AP) Christine Valentin (WOC)
Activity: ARICE presentations by Halldor Johannsson on ARICE and policy and developments with emphasis on the importance and benefits of international cross-discipline cooperation and data sharing and by Christine Valentin on Industry involvement.			
Aim of the workshop: The identification of joint industry and science community priorities for Arctic research and observations and increased business understanding and involvement:			
ARICE Participants at the event and their role Christine Valentin (WOC) – presenter Halldór Jóhannson (AP) – conference chair / presenter			

3. Online outreach

3.1. The ARICE webpage

www.arice.eu

Analytics – time-period 1 Jan 2018 – 30 November 2019

- 8405 individual user
- 86,9% new visitors with 13,1% returning visitors
- 33,673 Pageviews

Audience overview:

The audience overview shows how many visitors or users are visiting the webpage during a given period. The time-line shows the number of visitors per day, with the highest number corresponding to the 9 March 2018 with 138 visitors, on 12 April 2018 with 136 visitors, on 29 April 2019 with 120 visitors and on 17 June 2019 with 95 visitors. These dates are coincident with call announcements (head ups and call openings).

Most of the visits are coming from the United States or 22,5%, Germany 9,89%, United Kingdom 7,24% and Canada 6,74%.

Aquisition

Most visitors access the webpage directly (40,2%), 35,6% are visiting through organic search, 13,1% through referral, 10% through social media and 1,1% through email reference.

This is very interesting as organic search is shows how often the majority of visitors visit similar websites, organic search is a search by keywords through search engines.. Due to this fact, it is very important that this visit behaviour is studied and to optimise the search ability of the webpage.

The average pages views within ARICE are 2,68 which can be considered quite good as the unofficial industry standard is 2 pages per session

(<https://www.spinutech.com/digital-marketing/analytics/analysis/7-website-analytics-that-matter-most/>).

Browsers & OS:

The most frequent browser used for the webpage is Chrome with 45,28%, then Firefox with 21,3% and Safari with 14,84%.

Interestingly 76.93% of users access the webpage by using a desktop computer, 17,69% mobile and 2.38% by tablet.

Behavior Overview:

Most page views took place on 8 March 2018 with 454 views, on 12 April 2018 with 394 views, on 29 April 2019 with 375 views and on 3 September 2019 with 212 page views.

The most frequent page views, during the period, was on applications for ship-time with 5,171 (15,36%).

3.2. Social Media

Facebook page created in February 2018 with the name ARICE EU

The Facebook page has 156 followers / with gradually, but slowly, growing audience

Around 100 posts were performed during the reporting period.

A Twitter account was created February 2018 with the name ARICE EU

It has 72 followers / with gradually but very slowly growing audience.

Around 150 tweets were posted during the reporting period.

3.3. ARICE Newsletter

The newsletter was distributed using a list from the Arctic Portal, which is a compilation of contacts from projects, conferences and through partner's contribution such as IASC. It covers approximately 500 names. Apart from that, the newsletter was promoted through the ARICE, AWI and Arctic Portal outreach channels.

3.4. Online outreach from partners

AWI – www.awi.de

- Heads Up! ARICE calls for Ship-time proposals (08.03.2018): [https://mailchi.mp/6032fa1d0904/arice-heads-up-call-for-ship-time-proposals-186173?e=\[UNIQID\]](https://mailchi.mp/6032fa1d0904/arice-heads-up-call-for-ship-time-proposals-186173?e=[UNIQID])
- Kick-Off meeting: Nansen Legacy (09.03.2018) <https://www.awi.de/ueber-uns/service/presse-detailansicht/presse/kick-off-meeting-fuer-nansen-legacy.html>
- Press release: Making the Arctic accessible for excellent science (19.02.2019) <https://www.awi.de/en/about-us/service/press/press-release/making-the-arctic-accessible-for-excellent-science-1.html>
- ARICE Call open (11.04.2019): [https://mailchi.mp/6c7195b390d6/arice-heads-up-call-for-ship-time-proposals-231053?e=\[UNIQID\]](https://mailchi.mp/6c7195b390d6/arice-heads-up-call-for-ship-time-proposals-231053?e=[UNIQID])

ARCTIA – none

ARCTIC PORTAL - www.arcticportal.org

- Announcement – Press release (02.2018) <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2040-epb-apecs-webinar-the-eu-arctic-cluster>

- News / EPB-APECS Webinar: The EU Arctic Cluster (04.06.2018) <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2040-epb-apecs-webinar-the-eu-arctic-cluster>
- News / ARICE Call for Ship-Time Proposals 2018 (04.06.2018) <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2041-arice-call-for-ship-time-proposals-2018-now-open>
- News / ARICE first newsletter (11.02.2019) <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2099-arice-first-newsletter>
- News / Success story on Arice on EU webpage (07.03.2019) <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2121-success-story-on-arice-on-eu-webpage>
- News / Second newsletter - ARICE2019 Call for Ship-Time proposals (29.04.2019) <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2158-arice2019-call-for-ship-time-proposals-now-open>
- News / European Polar Board Excom (Arice mentioned) (31.05.2019) <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2172-new-members-elected-to-the-european-polar-board-excom>
- News / The EU-funded Arctic research projects meeting (26.06.2019) <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2182-the-eu-funded-arctic-research-projects-meet-in-brussels>
- News / MOSAIC Expedition and FrostByte Videos and ARICE's webpage (03.09.2019) <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2200-mosaic-expedition-and-frostbyte-videos-on-arice-s-webpage>
- News / Arice Webinar on Data Management, 17 December 2019 - <https://arcticportal.org/ap-library/news/2244-arice-webinar-on-data-management-17-december-2019-9-am-gmt>

BRITISH ANTARCTIC SURVEY - www.bas.ac.uk

- News / Working together to make the Arctic more... (02.02.2018) <https://www.bas.ac.uk/media-post/working-together-to-make-the-arctic-more-accessible-for-science/>
- News / Call for Arctic ship-based research proposals (20.04.2018) <https://www.bas.ac.uk/media-post/call-for-arctic-ship-based-research-proposals/>

CNRS - none

CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE – www.cnr.it

- News / ARICE H2020 Project – Transnational Access Opportunity (13.04.2018) <https://www.cnr.it/en/news/8053/arice-h2020-project-transnational-access-opportunity>

CSIC – none

DTU – www.dtu.dk

- News / Improving researchers' access to the Arctic (02.02.2018) <https://www.aqua.dtu.dk/english/news/2018/02/improving-research-access-to-arctic?id=fe131868-4248-4486-b920-f792447236f8>
- News / Bedre adgang til marin forskning i Arktis (05.02.2018) <https://www.aqua.dtu.dk/nyheder/2018/02/arice?id=d0dd67fe-42d7-439c-9ed6-f1df7fe17945>

FINNISH METEOROLOGICAL INSTITUTE - none

IOPAN – www.iopan.gda.pl

- International projects - ARICE Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium; A strategy for meeting the needs for marine-based research in the Arctic <https://www.iopan.pl/international.html>

NORSK POLARINSTITUT – None

SWEDISH POLAR RESEARCH SECRETARIAT – www.polar.se

- News / Icebreaker collaboration creates new opportunities ... (02.02.2018) <https://polar.se/en/news/icebreaker-collaboration-creates-new-opportunities-for-research-in-the-arctic/>
- News / ARICE call for proposals is now open (12.04.2018) <https://polar.se/en/news/arice-call-for-proposals-is-now-open/>
- News / ARICE 2019 call for ship-time proposals now open (29.04.2019) <https://polar.se/en/news/arice-2019-call-for-ship-time-proposals-now-open/>

UNIVERSITÉ LAVAL

- Research / ARICE: Arctic Research Icebreaker ... (01.01.2018 – last updated 15.10.2019) http://www.vrrc.ulaval.ca/fileadmin/ulaval_ca/Images/recherche/bd/projet/fiche/118978.html
- Projects funded at Laval University – ARICE http://www.vrrc.ulaval.ca/fileadmin/ulaval_ca/Images/recherche/bd/programme/fiche/2464_projet.html
- Directory of experts in the media – ARICE https://oraweb.ulaval.ca/pls/vrr/gexp_prof.html?p_no_dossier=54226
- Marcel Babin – Laval University – ARICE http://www.vrrc.ulaval.ca/fileadmin/ulaval_ca/Images/recherche/bd/chercheur/fiche/263509.html?id=32537
- Louis Fortier – Laval University – ARICE http://www.vrrc.ulaval.ca/fileadmin/ulaval_ca/Images/recherche/bd/chercheur/fiche/54226.html
- Marine Biology http://www.vrrc.ulaval.ca/fileadmin/ulaval_ca/Images/recherche/bd/projet/domaine/1620.html
- Department of Biology http://www.vrrc.ulaval.ca/fileadmin/ulaval_ca/Images/recherche/bd/projet/fac/dept/03602.html
- 2015 Arctic Circle Assembly <https://inq.ulaval.ca/docs/arctic-circle.pdf>
- Research projects at Laval University http://www.vrrc.ulaval.ca/fileadmin/ulaval_ca/Images/recherche/bd/projet/alpha/A.html

UAF – www.uaf.edu

- News / UAF joins international consortium of icebreakers operators (06.02.2018) <https://news.uaf.edu/uaf-joins-international-consortium-of-icebreaker-operators/>

WORLD OCEAN COUNCIL – www.oceancouncil.org

- News / ARICE Project opens Ship-time Proposals to Industry – 29 June 2018
<https://www.oceancouncil.org/media/arice-project-opens-ship-time-proposals-industry-29-june-2018/>
- EU Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium (ARICE) Project – General Assembly 2019
<https://www.oceancouncil.org/event/eu-arctic-research-icebreaker-consortium-arice-project-general-assembly/>
- ARICE 2019 Call for Ship-Time Proposals – 27 May 2019
<https://www.oceancouncil.org/media/arice-2019-call-for-ship-time-proposals-27-may-2019/>
- Arctic Circle 2019 <https://www.oceancouncil.org/event/arctic-circle-2019/>

APECS – www.apecs.is

- ARICE2019 Call for ship-time proposals – now Open <https://apecs.is/news/partner-news/3125-arice2019-call-for-ship-time-proposals-now-open.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- Call for Applications: MOSAiC School 2019 <https://apecs.is/news/apecs-news/2748-call-for-applications-mosaic-school-2019.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- Session 1 <https://apecs.is/events/past-event-highlights/events-2018/apecs-online-conference-2018/2490-session-1.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- Webinar „Pre-cruise Preparation and Risk Reduction <https://apecs.is/research/apecs-projects/arice/arice-webinars/2921-webinar-pre-cruise-preparation-and-risk-reduction.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- Webinar on Proposals writing, 25 April 2019 <https://apecs.is/research/apecs-projects/arice/arice-webinars/3285-webinar-proposal-writing.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- ARICE Press Release: Making the Arctic accessible for excellent science
<https://apecs.is/news/apecs-news/2326-arice-press-release-making-the-arctic-accessible-for-excellent-science-3.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- ARICE <https://apecs.is/research/apecs-projects/3034-arice.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- Heads Up! ARICE Calls for Ship Time 2018 <https://apecs.is/news/partner-news/2386-heads-up-arice-calls-for-ship-time-2018.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- APECS involvement in ARICE <https://apecs.is/research/apecs-projects/arice/3409-apecs-involvement-in-arice.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- ARICE Call for Ship-Time Proposals 2018 – NOW OPEN! (25.04.2018)
<https://apecs.is/news/apecs-news/2488-arice-call-for-ship-time-proposals-2018-now-open.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>
- ARICE Webinar on Data Management, 17 December 2019 <https://apecs.is/news/apecs-news/3636-arice-webinar-on-data-management-17-december-2019-9-am-gmt.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSjd>

4. Press

4.1. Press releases

Making the Arctic accessible for excellent science (19.02.2019). Simultaneous press release by the ARICE partners:

<https://www.awi.de/en/about-us/service/press/press-release/making-the-arctic-accessible-for-excellent-science-1.html>

<https://fathom.world/press-release-woc-brings-industry-engagement-international-arctic-research-icebreaker-consortium-arice/>

<https://www.apecs.is/news/apecs-news/2326-arice-press-release-making-the-arctic-accessible-for-excellent-science-3.html?highlight=WyJhcmljZSJD>

Ocean Council, 2019 <https://www.oceancouncil.org/media/arice-2019-call-for-ship-time-proposals-27-may-2019/>

4.2. Press /online-press Hits

February 2018

DGGV: Neue Wege in die Arktis für exzellente Wissenschaft

<https://www.dggv.de/en/news/news-articles/detailview/artikel/neue-wege-in-die-arkt-is-fuer-exzellente-wissenschaft.html>

Sea Technology, 2018, Arctic icebreaker consortium to facilitate research ship use, <https://sea-technology.com/arctic-icebreaker-consortium-to-facilitate-research-ship-use>

Frisch, Lauren (2018), Arctic Research consortium of the United States: NSF's Sikuliaq Joins a New Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium, <https://www.arcus.org/witness-the-arctic/2018/2/highlight/2>

Strategic environmental impact assessment of development of the Arctic, 2018. National Arctic Strategy Germany <https://www.arcticinfo.eu/en/germany>

Safety4Sea, 2018, EU funds Arctic research icebreaker consortium <https://safety4sea.com/eu-funds-arctic-research-icebreaker-consortium/>

Eureka Alert, 2018, Making the Arctic accessible for excellent science https://www.eurekaalert.org/pub_releases/2018-02/awih-mta020518.php

Weser Kurier - Bremerhaven: EU fördert Konsortium für Eisbrecher

Sonnabend, 3. Februar 2018

BREMERHAVEN | 19

10 Dinge, die man in Bremerhaven nicht tun sollte

In jeder Stadt gibt es Dinge, die man unbedingt wissen und tun sollte. Genauso gibt es Fallen, vor denen man sich besser hüten sollte. Diese zehn Regeln sollten Zugezogene und Urlauber in Bremerhaven lieber beachten. von STEFANIE JÜRGENSEN

Behaupten, dass die Stadt hässlich ist

Wer das vorschnell sagt, vergisst viele schöne Ecken wie die Parks, die Havenweiden, das Wieserstrandbad oder das Schaufenster Fischereihafen. Das Highlight ist und bleibt der Deich.

In der Nähe von Möwen etwas essen

Immer wieder klauen Möwen Fußgängern in der Innenstadt und am Deich im Sturzflug das Essen direkt aus der Hand. Möwen zu füttern, ist außerdem eine Ordnungswidrigkeit.

Einen Bogen um Fisch machen

In Bremerhaven gibt es frischen und leckeren Fisch zu entdecken. Ein Besuch im Fischereihafen ist deswegen Pflicht, ob Restaurant oder das Fischbratchen auf die Hand.

Nicht beim Eishockey mitfeiern

Eishockey wird in Bremerhaven großgeschrieben: Spielen die Fischtown Penguins, feiert die halbe

Moin ist die einzig wahre Begrüßung in Norddeutschland – egal, ob morgens, mittags, abends oder nachts. Die korrekte Antwort ist natürlich auch ein knappes Moin.

Sich über das Wetter beschweren

Nirgendwo scheint der Himmel so schön grau wie über Norddeutschland. Doch anstatt sich fortlaufend darüber zu beschweren, nehmen Nordlichter das einfach hin. Ist halt so.

Am Ufer parken bei Hochwasser

Diesen Fehler macht immer mal wieder einer und bereut es, wenn das Auto unter Wasser steht. Ist Hochwasser vorausgesetzt, lieber ein paar Meter weiter weg parken.

Bremen und Bremerhaven gleichsetzen

Ortsunkundige mag es überraschen: Aber Bremen und Bremerhaven liegen keines-

Arktis-Forschung

EU fördert Konsortium für Eisbrecher

BREMERHAVEN. Die EU fördert mit sechs Millionen Euro ein Konsortium für Forschungseisbrecher in der Arktis. Dabei ist die „Polarstern“. Für Wissenschaftler soll es leichter werden, einen Platz an Bord zu bekommen. Das Projekt mit dem Kürzel „ARICE“ wird über vier Jahre gefördert. 15 Partner aus 13 Ländern sind beteiligt, auch aus den USA und Kanada. Ziel des Konsortiums ist zudem, die Forschungsorte besser zu koordinieren. Das Alfred-Wegener-Institut (AWI) als Koordinator lädt kommenden Dienstag und Mittwoch zum Auftakt ins Deutsche Schiffahrtsmuseum ein.

Auch die Eisbrecher „Oden“ (Schweden), „Amundsen“ (Kanada) und „Sikuliaq“ (USA) kommen hinzu sowie die beiden im Bau befindlichen Schiffe „Kronprinz Haakon“ (Norwegen) und „Sir David Attenborough“ (UK) sind im Pool. Das Konsortium will außerdem mit der maritimen Wirtschaft zusammenarbeiten. So sollen Handels- und Tourismusschiffe, die den Arktischen Ozean befahren, Daten sammeln.

Die Hälfte des Fördergeldes wird dafür verwendet, Wissenschaftlern kostenlos Zugang zu den sechs Eisbrechern zu ermöglichen. Zum ersten Mal können sich europäische Wissenschaftler und internationale Partner dafür bewerben. „Wer mit an Bord kommt, entscheidet ausschließlich die wissenschaftliche Exzellenz des Forschungsantrags. Wir ernaunigen vor allem Nachwuchswissenschaftler und Forscher aus Ländern, die keinen direkten Zugang zu einem Eisbrecher haben, sich zu bewerben“, sagt Dr. Nicole Bielew, ARICE-Projekt Koordinatorin vom AWI. Eine Beteiligung ist auch bei der einjährigen Expedition 2019 mit der „Polarstern“ möglich, die in der Arktis mit dem Meereis driften wird. (aw)

Verein Solidar

Schulungen für

April 2018

Arctic Science Partnerships, 2018, <https://asp-net.org/content/arice-call-ship-time-proposals-2018-now-open>British Antarctic Survey, 2018 <https://www.bas.ac.uk/media-post/call-for-arctic-ship-based-research-proposals/>Research Connect, 2018. Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium (ARICE) Call for Ship-Time Proposals Now Open <https://www.researchconnect.eu/archive/arctic-research-icebreaker-consortium-arice-call-for-ship-time-proposals-now-open/>Euromarine Network, 2018. ARICE CALL 2018, <https://www.euromarinenetwork.eu/calls/arice-call-2018>

June 2018

The Maritime Executive (2018), ARICE Project opens Ship-time Proposals to Industry

<https://www.maritime-executive.com/corporate/arice-project-opens-ship-time-proposals-to-industry>

© ARICE Consortium

15/12/2019

Sea Technology, 2018, Arctic vessel operators invited to survey of data and instrumentation
<https://sea-technology.com/arctic-vessel-operators-invited-to-survey-of-data-and-instrumentation>

October 2018

ResearchConnect, 2019: Breaking the ice with international research mobility,
<https://www.researchconnect.eu/funding-views/breaking-the-ice-with-international-research-mobility/>

March 2019

European Commission, 2019: International cooperation boosts Arctic marine research, Available online at https://ec.europa.eu/research/infocentre/article_en.cfm?artid=49926

April 2019

Research Connect, 2019. Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium (ARICE) Call for Ship-Time Proposals Now Open, <https://www.researchconnect.eu/archive/arctic-research-icebreaker-consortium-arice-call-for-ship-time-proposals-now-open/>

All about shipping, 2019, **ARICE 2019 call for ship-time proposals**
<http://www.allaboutshipping.co.uk/2019/05/27/arice-2019-call-for-ship-time-proposals/>

October 2019

All about shipping, 2019, Breaking the Ice: Cooperation for Safe and Responsible Arctic Sea Routes
<http://www.allaboutshipping.co.uk/2019/10/04/breaking-the-ice-cooperation-for-safe-and-responsible-arctic-sea-routes/>